

ASSESSMENT OF THE GENERAL AND SPECIAL PHYSICAL FITNESS OF YOUNG PLAYERS

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Annotation: The article examines the use of assessment of general and special physical fitness of young football players based on modern views and approaches. The advantage of the recommended tests is given taking into account the number of heart contractions. The information provided is based on reliability.

Key words: modern tests, general training, special training, carrying the ball, running different distances, measurement results, test reliability.

In order to form an all-round mature and physically healthy generation in our country with a high level of culture, it is important to define the priority directions aimed at gaining skills and knowledge of the population in the field of physical education and sports, to introduce innovative forms and methods to the process of selecting (selection) talented athletes. attention is paid. To form a healthy way of life in our society, to create conditions for the young generation to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, to strengthen the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, among talented young people large-scale works aimed at the systematic organization of the selection of athletes are being carried out. "Measures to take the development of football in Uzbekistan to a completely new level" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, covering current issues in football, such as turning football into the most popular sport among the population, selecting young players with high talent on" decree No. PD 5887, to increase the interest of children and teenagers in playing football, to popularize amateur football, in this regard, to regularly organize football competitions in secondary schools, other educational institutions, neighborhoods and organizations Special attention is paid to organization.

In the practice of working with football players, a series of tests designed to monitor special training is widely used. This set includes the following tests:

- 30 m run;
- Carrying the ball "with a slalom" and hitting a small goal;
- Kicking the soccer ball far;
- Defensive actions (running forward, sideways and backwards);
- Accurate shots on goal.

For each test, a rating scale has been developed in the range from 1 to 100 points. However, according to the opinions of many coaches, from the point of view of the requirements of modern football, these tests are already outdated.

Tests designed to determine the special training of different skill players are also used in the form of overcoming the boundary line of obstacles, where the distance and the technical elements included in it (juggling alternately with feet and head, etc.) passing the ball to the

target, passing the ball to a long distance, passing the ball to the center) the total time of passing is counted separately. Points from 1 to 5 are assigned to each task, the total sum of points is considered as an assessment of the player's level of special training.

A set of tests designed to evaluate special training has been developed in order to select children for football teams organized at the Faculty of Sports Games of the Academy of Physical Education (Poznan). It consists of the following test types:

- Juggling alternately with the hips and the soles of the feet;
- Carrying the ball "with slalom";
- Hit the wall with the ball;
- accurate passing of the ball;
- Throwing shots at a 5x2 m goal.

Over time, this complex was not preserved in the practice of the educational process, due to the ineffectiveness of the rating scale and the not very rational selection of tests. In Germany, a set of tests consisting of 7 types of tests is widespread, in which the level of difficulty and evaluation in points varies depending on the age of the athlete. This set includes the following tests:

1. Juggling consists of a simple blow to the ball with the inside of the foot and the head. The grade is the average arithmetic value of the results of three methods.

2. Hitting the goal. The test taker makes 5 shots with his left foot and 5 shots with his right foot at the 1.5 m goal. The distance to the gate depends on the age of the subjects: for children - 8 m, for teenagers - 10 m, for young teenagers - 12 m, for older teenagers - 14 m, for young people - 16.5 m.

3. Passing the ball to the target. The test includes 10 passes on a square with sides of 4 or 5 m (5 times with the left foot, 5 times with the right foot, with the inner side of the foot), the passes are made from the following distance: children - 15 m (square 5 × 5 m), juniors - 15 m, juniors - 20 m, seniors - 25 m and youth - 30 m (square 4 × 4 m).

4. Throw shots at the 2x6 m goal after carrying the ball. 5 shots are made with the left foot to the left half of the goal, 5 shots are made with the right foot to the right half of the goal. 14 m, senior teenagers - 16.5 m and young people - 18 m.

5. Shot on goal after extra time. The ball thrown by the coach will be kicked into the indicated sector of the goal. It is necessary to make 5 shots with the left foot to the upper right sector of the goal and 5 shots with the right foot to the lower left sector of the goal (depending on where the goalkeeper is standing). Shots are made from the following distances: children - 4 m, teenagers - 5 m, juniors - 6 m, senior teenagers - 7 m and youth - 8 m. The size of the gate is 2 × 5 m.

6. Football "slalom". Carrying the ball along a 40 m long corridor (corridor) marked with flags. The time to cover the entire distance is estimated, the length of the distance depends on the age of the subjects.

7. Carrying the ball "with a slalom" and hitting the goal. The ball is carried between the flags placed after every 2 m, and then a shot is made on the side of the goal indicated by the coach. Shots are made from the following distance: children - 10 m, teenagers - 12 m, juniors - 14 m, seniors - 16.5 m, youth - 18 m. Before carrying, the athlete receives the ball thrown by the coach in a square of 3 × 3 m with his foot. The 2 x 6 m goal is shot 5 times with the left and right foot. *The age criteria in the set of tests are as follows: children (7–9 years old),*

teenagers (10–12 years old), young teenagers (13–14 years old), older teenagers (15–16 years old) and young people (17–18 years old).

The analysis of the literature shows that there are no uniform control tools designed to evaluate both general physical training and special training of football players during training. Often, indicators of these types of training are included in one set of tests. An example of this is the selection of athletes based on the growth dynamics of indicators in the following tests:

- 50 m run;
- 5x10 m "pendulum" run;
- Cooper's test;
- Standing long jump;
- Juggling in different ways;
- Hitting the ball far.

It is recommended to use a combination of tests such as the 1500 m run and the Cooper test in the practice of assessing the endurance of football players. The original method of assessing the special endurance of football players of different ages is the time to cross the "limit line of obstacles" (carrying the ball in different ways and hitting the goal), as well as the return of the heart rate to the initial size. is the speed of recovery. In this test, the results are closely correlated with the maximum oxygen consumption indicators (MOC).

In the process of selecting young players, general training tests (50 m run, standing long jump, throwing a stuffed ball, Cooper's test, 4x10 m "pendulum" run with changing directions), as well as small or subjective observation of players is used in games. The dynamics of the results in individual tests and the evaluation of the athletes' behavior in the game constitute the selection criteria.

In the training of football players, great importance is attached to the growth dynamics of technical training indicators, which are considered as one of the criteria for selecting young players. This set of tests includes:

- hitting the ball accurately;
- carrying the ball "with slalom";
- different forms of juggling;
- hitting the ball with the head;
- Throwing a stuffed ball weighing 3 kg.

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The original approach to collective assessment of the training of highly qualified players was proposed by the coaches of the Czech national team, and later by the staff of the European Football Federation. It is necessary to evaluate the fitness of the athlete based on the results of the following tests:

- the accuracy of shots on the goal;
- the speed of crossing a specific obstacle course;

- the quality of solving technical and tactical issues in the game (subjective assessment of the situation);
- the organism's reaction to training loads (based on NHK).

More specific criteria for evaluating the readiness of football players are given by M.A. developed by Godik (1980). According to him, the control should be carried out before the start of the season and he should assess the following:

- 15 m running speed (standing and moving);
- power (jump up);
- special endurance (running 10 × 30 m with a rest interval of 20-25 s);
- Condition of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems based on the Harvard test.

The synthetic assessment of players' fitness consists of crossing a special obstacle course five times (acceleration, braking, carrying the ball, hitting the goal) with an interval of 20 s between attempts. The score is calculated from the sum of the time spent on the test, as well as the comparison of the magnitude of the decrease in the NHK immediately after the completion of the task and after a 3-minute rest.

The general assessment of players' preparation for the start of the season should be made up of conditioning training (sports uniform) and special training. Tests that assess conditioning include:

- running for 15 m from a place and with movement;
- 30 and 60 m running;
- 10x30 m "pendulum" run;
- Cooper's test;
- standing up and jumping on one leg five times.

The following tests form the assessment of special training:

- to hit the ball far and accurately with the right and left foot.

Such an assessment of special training seems too narrow and one-sided. Technical preparation tests include:

- hitting the ball accurately;
- hitting the goal;
- juggling the ball in different ways.

Tests that assess special training are:

- 30 m run;
- 5x30 m "pendulum" run with a ball;
- long shots to the ball.

F.A. Iordanskaya (2011) takes a critical look at the commonly used 5x30m speed endurance test (also 7x50m) and proposes her own test based on the 14x25m shuttle run. The results of the conducted experiment show that the energetic cost of working in this test is 35.58% anaerobic and 31.58% aerobic-anaerobic component of energy supply. For the evaluation, the authors consider only the test execution time without analyzing the NHK and recovery time.

In Germany, as well as in some other countries of Western Europe, the test used to evaluate speed endurance is considered public. The execution of this test is based on a "pendulum run" between the sidelines of the field of play, the sidelines of the penalty area and the sidelines of the goal area. The sum of the distances is equal to 161 m, and the time to cover

it is the grade. This test was later modified: the same task is performed with a ball, which allows to determine the effect of carrying the ball on the final result of the test.

Running along a 15 m sided square, repeated 5 times with a 15 s rest interval, is also a reliable test to control the players' fitness. In this test, the total sum of the time to cover the distance (300 m) is evaluated, as well as the recovery time of NHK to 120 beats/min.

Another test that is very useful in pedagogical control is a test that allows you to determine the level of adaptation to a specialized load. It consists of a high start and a run of 30 m at maximum speed, as well as recording of the NHK during the first 10 s after the run, at the beginning of the second and third minutes of rest. The test is performed twice - the first time - 3 minutes after warming up the body, and the second time - 3 minutes after the completion of all exercises of the main part of the training session.

Summary. The analysis of the researched literature and reliable data shows that running distances of 20-40 m, maximum 60 m are often used to evaluate the speed of the players' movements. The new proposals are tests designed to determine quickness, which diagnose acceleration from the start in sections of 10-20 m and reaching maximum running speed in sections of 30-40 m. The reliability of the assessment tests recommended by us has been advanced by leading scientists from different countries.

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